

STUDY ON NORMALIZATION OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF JUTE-GLASS/VINYLESTER HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Fiber Reinforced Plastic(FRP) have good specific strength, and stiffness as well as relatively low cost. Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic (GFRP) is one of well-known FRP materials due to their lightweight, high specific strength and specific stiffness. Nowadays it is widely used in many industries. However, GFRP shows bad damping performance and it limit their application to automotive and sports industry. In literature, Natural fiber mixed Glass/Natural fiber hybrid composites have good damping performance [1-5].

The vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process is capable of manufacturing large-scale fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) parts with low tooling cost [6]. But when hybrid composites were made by VARTM, it is difficult to conclude that hybrid composites have better performance than CFRP and GFRP because of different thickness. The thickness of FRP fabricated by VARTM process is depends on the thickness of reinforcement and vacuum pressure. Also, the thickness of FRP can be predicted by measurement of the thickness of each lamina. However, two composites which have same reinforcement but different thickness shows different mechanical properties. Especially, in hybrid composites it is more difficult to predict the mechanical properties with different thickness. In this study, Jute/Glass hybrid composites were fabricated and normalizations were conducted for comparison with different thickness hybrid composites.

In this study, the combination of synthetic and natural fibers are used as reinforcement and vinyl ester have used as matrix for development of hybrid composites which have improved damping properties. After, tensile and flexural test were conducted. Table 1 and 2 shows fabricate schedule for hybrid composites. The results show that Jute/Glass hybrid composites have improved mechanical properties than previous study which reported that Jute/Glass hybrid composites have low mechanical properties. These different results are the reason of different thickness due to VARTM process. Despite Jute/Glass hybrid composites have improved properties, these composites have low mechanical properties than GFRP because jute fiber have low mechanical properties and density. Low density will lead to decrease the mechanical properties with decrease the fiber volume fraction.

Fig. 1 Vacuum assisted Resin Transfer Molding

Table 1 Fabrication schedule for thickness effect

No.	Glass fabric	Jute fabric
1	2	2
2	4	4
3	6	6

Table 2 Fabrication schedule for structure effect

<i>No.</i>	<i>Glass fabric</i>	<i>Jute fabric</i>
1	4	2
2	4	4
3	4	6

Here are the conclusions. If the GFRP and Jute/Glass Hybrid composites are made as same thickness, the properties of Jute/Glass hybrid composites are lower than GFRP. However Jute/glass hybrid composites show acceptable properties and high damping performance for application to car interior and specific sports goods.

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